

Molecular Assets: Authoritative Intelligence

*"Tell me what you know not
what you think"...*

Stephen K. Boyer Ph.D.
Philadelphia Conference
May 2026

It's been a while!

Internet Patent Access & Search: 1997–2026

From the first free patent servers to intelligent, AI-powered discovery

The Journey: From the groundbreaking IBM Patent Server in 1997 to today's AI-enhanced, chemistry-aware, globally connected search experiences, Internet patent access has evolved from specialist tools to intelligent platforms that empower innovators worldwide.

Natural language searches of authoritative data using a Customized Large Language Model (LLM)

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Why we started Molecular Assets or How we got to now

Benazepril Patent

The Prompt

Who invented
benazepril ?

~2023

Bard / ChatGPT

Mahesh Desai
a chemist at Hoechst

Result

United States Patent [19]

Watthey

[11] 4,410,520

[45] Oct. 18, 1983

[54] 3-AMINO-[1]-BENZAZEPIN-2-ONE-1-ALKANOIC ACIDS

[75] Inventor: Jeffrey W. H. Watthey, Chappaqua, N.Y.

[73] Assignee: Ciba-Geigy Corporation, Ardsley, N.Y.

[21] Appl. No.: 398,241

[22] Filed: Jul. 19, 1982

Related U.S. Application Data

[63] Continuation-in-part of Ser. No. 319,863, Nov. 9, 1981, abandoned, which is a continuation-in-part of Ser. No. 291,907, Aug. 11, 1981, abandoned.

[51] Int. Cl.³ C07D 223/16; A61K 31/55

[52] U.S. Cl. 424/244; 260/239.3 B;

[58] Field of Search 260/239.3 B, 239.3 T;

424/244

References Cited

U.S. PATENT DOCUMENTS

3,748,321 7/1973 Krapcho 260/239 BB

FOREIGN PATENT DOCUMENTS

673856 6/1966 Belgium 260/239.3 B

12401 1/1980 European Pat. Off. 564/194

26640 4/1981 European Pat. Off. 548/550

46291 2/1982 European Pat. Off. 260/239.3 B

61187 9/1982 European Pat. Off. 260/239.3 B

2714442 10/1977 Fed. Rep. of Germany ... 260/239.3

49-28753 7/1974 Japan 260/239.3 B
49-28754 7/1974 Japan 260/239.3 B
1305278 1/1973 United Kingdom 260/239.3 B
2095252 9/1982 United Kingdom 546/147

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

Stewart, "Australian J. of Chemistry", vol. 33 (1980), pp. 633-640.

Friedinger et al., "J. Org. Chem.", vol. 47, pp. 104-109 (1982).

Australian J. Chem., vol. 33, 633 (1980).

Japan 74-028753, 7/29/1974, CA 82, 139978m (1975).

Japn 74-028754, 7/29/1974, CA 82, 139981g (1975).

Paquette et al., J. Organic Chemistry, vol. 34, pp. 2879-2880, (1969).

Smith et al., J. Medicinal Chemistry, vol. 24, pp. 104-109, (1981).

Patchett et al., Nature, vol. 288, pp. 280-283, (1980).

J. Org. Chem., vol. 34, 2879 (1969).

J. Med. Chem., vol. 24, 104 (1981).

Nature, vol. 288, 280 (1980).

Primary Examiner—Robert T. Bond

Attorney, Agent, or Firm—Norbert Gruenfeld

[57] ABSTRACT

Variously substituted 1-carboxymethyl-3-(carboxymethylamino)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1H-[1]benzazepin-2-ones and functional derivatives are angiotension converting enzyme inhibitors and are useful as antihypertensive agents. Synthesis of, compositions and methods of treatment utilizing such compounds are included.

29 Claims, No Drawings

What is our AI?

Authoritative Intelligence

Gemini and ChatGPT are transformer-based large language models

- Rely on expensive statistical modeling of **very large sets of text chunks**
- Transform natural language queries into statistically most likely answers
- High confidence for frequent relationships
- Low confidence for rare relationships
- Hallucination included

Authoritative Intelligence is a vetted-info-based large language model

- Relies on large sets of ***authoritative facts in validated databases***
- Translates natural language queries into complex expert SQL queries
- Explicit statistics for frequent relationships
- High precision - even for rare relationships
- No hallucination

Authoritative Intelligence Technology

Automated LLMs transform natural language queries into complex SQL queries that produce results transformed back into natural language

Authoritative Intelligence Technology

Technology builds on:

- proprietary, trained LLMs based on both ChatGPT & Gemini for generating SQL queries
- hundreds of curated BigQuery SQL database tables
- comprising terabytes of validated data from trusted sources
- input extracted from structured data in open access and proprietary databases, millions of scientific papers, and patent documents
- translated from > 58 different languages

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Generic Drugs & Revenues

The Prompt

"Show me the manufacturers of all generic Benazepril formulations (Benazepril HCl, Benazepril/Hydrochlorothiazide, Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril) and report their total Medicare Part D revenues for 2023."

ChatGPT (Nov 24, 2025):

Short answer: I *can't* reliably give you the full 2023 manufacturer list and dollar amounts from here—

Chat GPT (April 29, 2026) :

What you're asking for sounds straightforward but actually isn't directly available in any single public dataset—and in one key respect, it's not even fully *possible* from public data.

Here's the precise breakdown of what can (and cannot) be done, with concrete manufacturer lists and how Medicare revenue data works.

Authoritative Intelligence

manufacturer	generic_name	total_spent_usd
Overall	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$45,430,884.68
Overall	Benazepril HCl	\$37,037,536.15
Aurobindo Pharm	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$15,920,840.91
Aurobindo Pharm	Benazepril HCl	\$15,886,800.71
Solco Healthcar	Benazepril HCl	\$14,864,832.04
Overall	Benazepril/Hydrochlorothiazide	\$13,857,116.18
Lupin Pharmaceu	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$12,406,868.14
Dr.Reddy'S Lab	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$7,717,087.57
Sandoz	Benazepril/Hydrochlorothiazide	\$7,343,011.10
Amneal Pharmace	Benazepril HCl	\$6,219,884.01
Rising Pharm	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$4,274,190.52
Ani Pharmaceuti	Benazepril/Hydrochlorothiazide	\$3,802,874.12
Novartis/Sandoz	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$2,992,163.29
Padagis	Benazepril/Hydrochlorothiazide	\$2,650,431.05
Bluepoint Labor	Amlodipine Besylate/Benazepril	\$2,119,734.25

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Co-Occurrence

The Prompt

“What diseases co-occur in the claims of patents with JAK3”

ChatGPT (April 29, 2026):

In short: diseases most frequently co-claimed with JAK3 inhibition are atopic dermatitis, rheumatoid arthritis, IBD, lupus, psoriasis, and transplant rejection—representing conditions where cytokine and T-cell signaling via the common γ -chain plays a central pathological role.

QABot: Co-occurrence of JAK3 with diseases

Disease / Condition	Patent Count	Disease / Condition	Patent Count
cancer disorder	6195	Pancreatic neoplasm	912
Autoimmune disease	3542	diabetes mellitus	885
rheumatoid arthritis	2084	malignant pancreatic neoplasm	878
Lymphomas	1487	pancreatic carcinoma	867
leukemia	1429	Ovarian cancer	853
inflammatory disease	1414	Lung neoplasm malignant	851
asthma	1408	Ovarian neoplasm	838
multiple sclerosis	1399	Breast neoplasm	836
Psoriasis	1249	Hypersensitivity	833
Transplant rejections	1119	Breast cancer	830
melanoma	1014	pancreatic cancer	810
syndromic disease	986	Alzheimer disease	734
Colon cancer	969		
Pancreatic neoplasm	923		
diabetes mellitus	912		
malignant pancreatic neoplasm	885		
	878		

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: CPC Analysis

The Prompt

Obtain a count of distinct inchi-keys in patents having cpc code starting with **A01P** for three companies: Bayer, Syngenta, and Corteva (biocidal, pest repellent, pest attractant or plant growth regulators)

ChatGPT (Dec 5, 2025):

I'm sorry – I cannot directly compute a reliable count of distinct InChI-Keys in patents for those companies (Bayer, Syngenta, Corteva) restricted to CPC code starting with "A01P" – because I do not have automated access to a global patent corpus that includes **both** (a) full chemical structure annotations (including InChI-Keys) **and** (b) company-assignee + CPC metadata in a form that supports such aggregation.

QABot: Found

Company	Distinct Compounds (InChIKeys)
Syngenta	16,537
Bayer	12,840
Corteva	8,033

Authoritative Intelligence: Examples

Example Questions

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Compounds in Claims

The Prompt

“Find all of the compounds (smiles) in the claims from the company Genentech. Show only those where the inchikeys are not blank”

The Results
(viewed in DataWarrior)

All Compounds Found 531,248

of Distinct Compounds 32,288

of Distinct Patents WW 12,245

of Co-Assignees 871

Table	publication_number	assignee_names	Structure of smiles	Equivalent Row Count	inchikey	smiles
2239	CA-2711759-A1 EP-2252616-A1 US-2011127216-A1 WO-2009097446-A1	GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE ROCHE DOTSON IENNA FERHEFFRON		4	NEJAFMTSVQYQP-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>N=1C=2NC(=C=CC2 C)=NC=1C1=CC=CC2 NN2</chem>
2239	AU-2009231885-A1 CA-2719032-A1 US-2009237567-A1 WO-2009123971-A1	HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC		4	SQOXIAFABRLXNQ-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>COC(=O)C1=CC(N)=N 1)-CC2=C(C1=NC=C C2</chem>
2239	AU-2015202365-A1 AU-2015252365-A1 AU-2016253677-A1 AU-2016253677-A1	GENENTECH INC		4	KUUEXLRLPQQJ-HNNXBMFYSA-N	<chem>C1([C@H](O)CN1)C2=C =CC2=C(C(Br)=CC=C1 CNCC1</chem>
2239	AU-2005216251-A1 CA-2556752-A1 CA-2556752-C EP-1718667-B1	GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC HOFFTE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC		4	HYMFSAFINFTIFH-NGSRAFSJSA-N	<chem>O=C1C(OC)=C(C(C)=C CC@N)1C(O)(C=O)C@H 2C(=C@N)1N2[C@@H]2</chem>
2239	AU-2009516251-A1 CA-2556752-A1 CA-2556752-C EP-1718667-B1	GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC HOFFTE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC GENENTECH INC SEATTLE GENETICS INC		4	HYMFSAFINFTIFH-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>O=C1C(OC)=C(C(C)=C C(O)(CN)=O)C1C(O) 1</chem>
2239	AU-2009251291-A1 CA-2721851-A1 US-2009318411-A1 WO-2009146406-A1	HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE GENENTECH INC GENENTECH INC HOFFMANN LA ROCHE CASTANEDO		4	DGAMBEREULCPV-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>N1=C2N(CCO)C=NC2 OCC2)N=C1C1=CC=C</chem>
2239	US-10028942-B2 US-10028942-B2 US-2016000228-A1 US-9550777-B2	GENENTECH INC		4	GFPKESFPAICYX-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>C1CNC(=O)C(CCC1)C 2=C(C(C)=C(C)N3=C N1C</chem>
2239	AU-2007333243-A1 CA-2671845-A1 CA-2671845-C EP-2114950-A2	GENENTECH INC DANIEL SUTHERLIN CASTANEDO,GEORGETTE BAXLSS TRACY CHUCKOWRE IRIAN DOTSON IENNA FERJOLKES Adrian GOLDSMITH RICHARD GUNZNER JANET HEFFRON		4	JJALFTHLLNWBCV-UHFFFAOYSA-N	<chem>C=25C(C1)(O)C=CC =25C(N)=NC=2)=NC= OCC1</chem>

2100 of 2548 MB Selected: Visible:32288 Total:32288

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Clinical Trials

The Prompt

“Show me the chemical structures (smiles) for Genentech compounds currently in clinical trials. Also show the related associated data”

The Results
(viewed in DataWarrior)

Found 17 Clinical trials with
NCTIDs & Smiles

- 6 in phase 1
- 4 in phase 1/2 or 1/3
- 6 in phase 2
- 1 in phase 4

5 Active but not recruiting

10 Active/recruiting

14 Different targets

7 Different indications

The screenshot shows the DataWarrior interface with a table of clinical trial data. The table has columns for Clinical Trial ID, Compound, Trial data, Aliases, Mechanism, Status, Structure of SMILES, and SMILES. Four rows are visible, showing details for Entrectinib, Erlotinib, Giredestrant, and Tepotinib. The right sidebar shows a Category Browser with a list of Clinical Trial IDs and a Compound search field. The bottom status bar indicates 77 of 128 MB, 1 selected, 17 visible, and 17 total items.

	Clinical Trial ID	Compound	Trial data	Aliases	Mechanism	Status	Structure of SMILES	SMILES
5	NCT04302020	Entrectinib	Phase 2	Rozyltrek	NTRK/ROS1/ Recruiting	NSCLC		CN1CCN(CC1)C2=cC...
6	NCT04449874	Erlotinib	Phase 1	Tarceva	EGFR inhibitor	Active not rec		COCCOC1=c(C)c...
7	NCT03332797	Giredestrant	Phase 1/3	GDC-9545;	Oral SERD / Active/recruit	breast cancer		C[C@@H]1CC2=cC...
8	NCT03360712	Tepotinib	Phase 1	Tepmetko	MET inhibitor	Active not rec		C1=CC(=CC=C1)C=...

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Finding Compounds

The Prompt

"Find patents assigned to Genentech with inventor Purkey. For these patents find compounds in claims. collect the distinct assignee, inventor, inchikey, smiles"

The Results

(viewed in DataWarrior)

- 1,182 distinct cpds in claims

DataWarrior File Edit Data Chemistry Database List Macro Help

Purkey_cpds.tsv

Table	assignee	inventor	Structure of smiles	inchikey	smiles
5	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS		ADWGCMDWWMXFK-FQEVSTJZSA-N	C1(CC1)C(@H)(C=O)NJC=
6	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS EDWARD		AEGMQIFWUQCAES-AWEZNCQLSA-N	C1(CC1)C(@H)(C=O)NJC=
7	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS		AEGNCPBRSDYJKO-GFCCVEGCSA-N	NC=1OC2=C(N=1)C=C(C=C
8	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS		AEGNCPBRSDYJKO-LBPRGRZSA-N	NC=1OC2=C(N=1)C=C(C=C
9	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS		AEQIUWNGRWMBD-UHFFFAOYSA-N	C1=C2N(C(C)C)C=NC2=CN=
10	GENENTECH INC	PURKEY HANS		AFLVQWXUMLWGA-UHFFFAOYSA-N	BrC=1C=C2C3=C(N=C(N3C

1641 of 2548 MB Selected: Visible:1182 Total:1182

Category Browser

Column: inventor

assignee: contains

inventor: PURKEY HANS PURKEY HANS EDWARD

inchikey: contains

Structure of smiles: contains

smiles: contains

Column Name	Value
assignee	GENENTECH INC
inventor	PURKEY HANS
inchikey	ADWGCMDWWMXFK-FQ...
smiles	C1(CC1)C(@H)(C=O)N

Structure of smiles

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: Legal Status

The Prompt

“Show me the maintenance status of all US patents assigned to Genentech”

Fees (total) 9,036

Exp (expired) 946

551 (4th yr) 342

552 (8th yr) 259

553 (12 yr) 1,405

185 (12 yr) 83

DataWarrior File Edit Data Chemistry Database List Macro Help

Genentech_Maint_Fees_Status.tsv

Table	publication_number	assignee_names	title	family_id	filing_date	grant_date	maintenance_fee	fee_code	maintenance_fee_description	country
1316	US-5702946-A	GENENTECH INC	Anti-IL-8 monoclonal antibodies	22763963	19950301	19970120	20091230	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1317	US-5677264-A	GENENTECH INC	Anti-IL-8 antibody fragments	22763963	19950301	19971104	20091231	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1318	US-5653996-A	GENENTECH INC	Method for preparing liposomes	22188126	19950317	19970805	20090805	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1319	US-5645110-A	GENENTECH INC	Method for treating capsulless sars	23036111	19940701	19970624	20090624	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1320	US-5605689-A	GENENTECH INC	Treatment of HIV-associated immu	24848900	19940603	19971021	20090225	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1321	US-5595889-A	GENENTECH INC	Recombinant methods of making II	27002811	19940424	19960627	20091121	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1322	US-5589363-A	GENENTECH INC	DNA encoding tissue factor mutat	24871593	19940520	19961231	20081231	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1323	US-5583013-A	GENENTECH INC	Method and means for microbial p	25774577	19950502	19961210	20001210	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1324	US-5645616-A	GENENTECH INC	Method for predicting and/or prev	23230316	19950427	19960518	20080818	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1325	US-5543503-A	GENENTECH INC	Antibodies to human IL-8: CP1b il	22129886	19930611	19960805	20080317	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1326	US-5424919-A	GENENTECH INC	Human growth hormone	26738790	19940527	19950316	20071126	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1327	US-5420220-A	GENENTECH INC	Method and means for microbial;	27120638	19950101	19951010	20051116	EXP.	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee	United States
1328	US-5246787-A	GENENTECH INC	Method for in-vitro epikephalms	27485173	19931116	19931116	20011116	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1329	US-5222335-A	GENENTECH INC	Amino acid sequence determinati	25126956	19911025	19930662	20010624	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1330	US-5222439-A	GENENTECH INC	Method and means for microbial;	27068494	19920115	19930622	20010624	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1331	US-5222119-A	GENENTECH INC	Method of stimulating immune res	29093945	19950236	19930718	20010615	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1332	US-5410133-B2	GENENTECH INC	Anti-FcγR3 antibodies and method	24340706	20190410	20200802	20260106	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1334	US-11390678-B2	GENENTECH INC	Compositions and methods for the	40873503	20190809	20220719	20251218	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1334	US-11390758-B2	GENENTECH INC	Methods and compositions for stu	58223922	20190822	20220712	20251218	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1335	US-11379561-B2	GENENTECH INC	Methods and formulations for red	61028818	20190923	20220705	20251119	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1337	US-11370833-B2	GENENTECH INC	Antibody formulations	54238581	20180703	20220628	20251119	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States
1338	US-11379836-B2	GENENTECH INC	Methods of conjugating an agent	61658690	20170126	20220628	20251119	M1551	Payment of Maintenance Fee, 4th Year	United States

1087 of 2548 MB Selected: 0 Visible: 9035 Total: 9035

Category Browser
Column: publication_number
publication_number
title
family_id
filing_date
grant_date
country

Column Name	Value
publication_number	US-5702946-A
title	Anti-IL-8
family_id	22763963
filing_date	19950301
grant_date	19970120
country	United States
assignee_names	GENENTECH INC
application_number	US-08/389611
maintenance_fee	20091230
maintenance_fee_code	EXP.
maintenance_fee_descr	Patent Expired for Failure to Pay Maintenance Fee

Authoritative Intelligence Examples: CPC Analysis

The Prompt

“Find compounds in the claims section of Bayer patents with CPC A01N25, and return one row per distinct inchikey with the associated smiles, publication number, assignee and cpc code”

The Results

- 7,607 distinct compounds in claims

* A01N 25/00 Biocides, pest repellants or attractants, or plant growth regulators, ...

DataWarrior File Edit Data Chemistry Database List Macro Help

Bayer_CPC_A01N25.tsv

publication_number	assignee	Structure of smiles	cpc_code	inchikey	smiles
5459	BR-112019012249-A2	BAYER AG	A01N25/32	YTCIYOXHHQLDEI-SNVBACLBSA-N	C1C@N1(C=O)CCCC
5460	BR-112019012249-A2	BAYER AG	A01N25/32	YTCIYOXHHQLDEI-UHFFFAOYSA-N	C-12C(C)CC(C)C(C)C2
5461	JP-2000204085-A	NIPPON BAYER AGROCHEM CO LTD	A01N25/04	XTKDAFGWCDAMPY-UHFFFAOYSA-N	C1=CC(F)=CC=C1Cl
5462	DE-102004023332-A1	BAYER CROPSCIENCE GMBH	A01N25/32	BQCVDMQFMWYSC-UHFFFAOYSA-N	O=C1NCCCN(C)C(C)C2
5463	US-2016262393-A1	BAYER CROPSCIENCE AG	A01N25/30	QPMDERQDIYINCENC-UHFFFAOYSA-N	N1=C(C)CN=NC(C)C
5464	CA-3219384-A1	BAYER AG	A01N25/32	PMJRLYSMEOLBIU-UHFFFAOYSA-N	COC(=O)C1=CC2=C
5465	CA-3219384-A1	BAYER AG	A01N25/32	XWRQTTLWMHKCFEC-UHFFFAOYSA-N	C1=C(C)C(SCC)-O)C
5466	US-2016227788-A1	BAYER CROPSCIENCE LP	A01N25/02	XWRQTTLWMHKCFEC-LGMDPLHSA-N	C1=C(C)C(SCC)-O)C
5467	EP-1128724-B1	BAYER AG	A01N25/34	FHYFDNQZCQSQAI-UHFFFAOYSA-N	C1=C2N(C)C=C-C-C(C)C
5468	EP-4156936-A1	BAYER AG	A01N25/30	LDPHNKTALTVSV-UHFFFAOYSA-N	CON(C1=O)C1CC1C1C

1432 of 2548 MB Selected: 1 Visible: 7607 Total: 7607

Category Browser
Column: inchikey
inchikey contains
Structure of smiles contains 100%
smiles contains
publication_number contains
assignee contains
cpc_code contains

Column Name	Value
inchikey	YTCIYOXHHQLDEI-SNVBACLBSA-N
smiles	C1C@N1(C=O)CCCC
publication_number	BR-112019012249-A2
assignee	BAYER AG
cpc_code	A01N25/32

Structure of smiles

Authoritative Intelligence: Example: Pfizer's Macrocylic compounds

The Prompt

Find distinct Pfizer compounds that are macrocyclic with length larger than 8. Also show me the patent numbers and the associated targets and bioactivities of the compounds. Use the patent tables to find the compounds assigned to Pfizer

The Results

- 395 distinct
- macrocyclic compounds
- with
- Chain length >8
- Bioactivities
- Gene symbols
- Assays & values

	pfizer_patent_numbers	cid	Structure of smiles	macrocycle_length	gene_symbols	assay_types	bioactivity_re-cords	min_assay_value	max_assay_value	Inchikey	smiles
143	AU-2009321221-B2; BR-P0920936-A2; CA-2743030-A1; CA-2743030-C; ES-2415430-T3; ES-2415430-T9; ME-01144-8; PT-2370442-E; US-2011144129-A1; US-2013157008-A1; US-8283303-B2; US-8946413-B2; WO-2010061329-A1	466371.0		12	CD4; SORT1	IC50	4	0.21	0.38	SRJIECKMIRMJ-UHFFFAOYSA-N	CC1=CC=C
144	AU-2011228699-B2; DK-2547679-T3; EP-1340979-A3; US-2003171293-A1; WO-03073107-A2; WO-03073107-A3	16133803.0		38	BLM; GAA; GAPDH; GBA; GCNSL2; GLA; MEN1; MLI; MRGRK2; Mgrprb2; POLK; THRB; VDR	Activity; EC50; Potency	19	0.14	79.4328	DDRPLNQINRBR1-WYYADCIBA-N	C1C=@H1C@C
145	AU-2011228699-B2; DK-2547679-T3; ES-2233282-T3; ES-2557895-T3	100925880.		23	HCRT1; HCRT2	EC50; Ki	15	0.00013	10.0	OFNHCAUYYOTPM-IIOAANCSA-N	C1C=@H1C1
146	AU-2012311184-A1; CA-2847540-A1; CA-2904797-A1; EP-2758402-A1; EP-2758402-B1; EP-2758402-B9; EP-2908336-A2; ES-2575710-T3; ES-2575710-T9; KR-20140059246-A; MX-2014003501-A; TW-201113723-A; TW-1492946-B; US-2013079324-A1	118031609.		13	F11	Ki	1	6.174	6.174	DEKPODSYVPCPW-2GZKFVETSA-N	C1CCC2=C
147	AU-2013229173-A1; AU-2013229173-B2; AU-2013365908-A1; AU-2015275826-A1; AU-2021325426-A1; AU-2021404974-A1; AU-2021404974-A9; BR-112014022106-B1; BR-112015014678-B1; AU-2013229173-A1; US-2014135339-A1; US-9133215-B2	108150.0		10	ABC1; AHR; AR; ATAD5; ATRX2; Cdkp32; CYP19A1; CYP3A4; DRD3; ESR1; GPX1; GPX4; IFNB1; KCN2; NR1I2; NR3C1; PARG1; PPARG; RARGF3; RARGF4; SYK; TDP1; TP53; WHSC1	FC; Potency	97	0.0014	223.872	PKVRCRHMYSYX-AIFWHQITSA-N	CC1=CC=
148	AU-2013229173-A1; US-2014135339-A1; US-9133215-B2	89816720.0		12	ALK; NTRK2	IC50; Ki	8	0.00056	0.065	MOENETCLMCOREY-CFCCVCGSA-N	C1C=@H1C1

72 of 98 MB Selected: Visible:395 Total:395

Data Sources

Two interfaces: Standalone App or Agentic Skill

Standalone app

- Browser-based interface
- Useful for in-depth conversations
- Spreadsheet-like tables
- Filter results
- Generates Python in sandbox
 - Plots
 - Libraries - RDKit, etc.

Agentic skill

- Interfaces to LLM frameworks
 - Claude Code
 - OpenAI Codex
 - Google Gemini
 - Other open frameworks
- Interacts with other agents
- Produces JSON and MD tables

System Architecture - Standalone App

Standalone App Interface

Authoritative Science Assistant
Interactive exploration for patents, compounds, assays, and biology data.
GCP Project ID: bqquery

Options: CONVERSATIONAL OFF WEB ASSIST ON RUN PYTHON ON LLM Gemini ChatGPT

Print New session Logout

Filters/sorting

publication...	title	family_id	filing...	grant...	assignee_names	country
ES-8602119-A1	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations, meth...	23920101	19840406	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Spain
EP-0125023-A1	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations, meth...	23920101	19840406	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	European Patent Of
DE-3484664-D1	RECOMBINANT IMMUNOGLOBULIN PREPARATI...	23920101	19840406	19910711	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Germany
EP-0125023-B2	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19840406	20020313	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	European Patent Of
JP-S60155132-A	Recombined immunoglobulin	23920101	19840406	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Japan
IL-71455-A0	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19840406	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Israel
ES-531372-A0	METHOD FOR PREPARING IMMUNOGLOBULINS ...	23920101	19840406	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Spain
ZA-842583-B	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19840405	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	South Africa
DK-179684-A	IMMUNOGLOBULINS AND FRAGMENTS PROD...	23920101	19840405	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Denmark
DK-174048-B1	Non-glycosylated chimeric immunoglobulin species	23920101	19840405	20020506	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Denmark
IE-57198-B1	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations, meth...	23920101	19840405	0	GENENTECH INC	Ireland
DK-179684-D0	IMMUNOGLOBULINS AND FRAGMENTS PROD...	23920101	19840405	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Denmark
NZ-222543-A	Altered recombinant immunoglobulins	23920101	19840404	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	New Zealand
NZ-222542-A	Production of chimeric immunoglobulins, expressi...	23920101	19840404	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	New Zealand
AU-598441-B2	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19840404	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	Australia
NZ-207746-A	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparation	23920101	19840404	0	GENENTECH INC HOPE CITY	New Zealand
AU-2642984-A	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19840404	0	HOPE CITY GENENTECH INC	Australia
US-4816567-A	Recombinant immunoglobulin preparations	23920101	19830408	19890328	GENENTECH INC	United States

Export/save: Export HTML, Export TSV, Save filtered table in BigQuery

User prompt: Show me patents from Genentech with CPC A01N25

Send

System Architecture - Agentic Skill

Magic Happens Here !

New Opportunities to Collaborate

Molecular Assets currently collaborates with :

- **Molgenie on New Curation of Chemical Content**
- **Google bridging BigQuery & Graph Databases**
- **Kineviz on BigQuery & visualization**

Join us....

Molecular Assets + Google + KineViz

Bridging Relational dBs (SQL) & Object Orented (Graph dBs)

Select :

- Disease
- Genes
- Assay type
- Assay values
- Assay threshold
- Other properties

Visualized with Kineviz

Disease -> Gene -> Compound -> Assay Associations

Watch the short video from Google Next 2025 in Las Vegas <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=skF9Svsc2lq>

Authoritative Intelligence: New Data Examples from Images

Using novel AI supported data extraction methods for patent images increase precision and recall

EP1678168B1_C0003.tif

MolScribe
C++

556 correct compounds
from EP-1678168-B1

WO2021090855A1_D0437_3.tif

Decimer
C++

2,858 correct compounds
from WO-2021090855-A1

Comparing software tools for optical
chemical structure recognition
A Krasnov, SJ Barnabas, T Boehme,
SK Boyer, L Weber
Digital Discovery 2024
DOI:10.1039/d3dd00228d

Authoritative Intelligence: New Data Examples from Tables

Enumeration methods for tables increase precision and recall: **49,050 single compounds from EP-2550280-B1:**

(19) **EP 2 550 280 B1**

(12) **EUROPEAN PATENT SPECIFICATION**

(45) Date of publication and mention of the grant of the patent: 26.02.2014 Bulletin 2014/09

(21) Application number: 11708880.7

(22) Date of filing: 18.03.2011

(54) **PYRIDOTHIAZINES HAVING HERBICIDAL ACTION**
PYRIDOTHIAZINE MIT HERBIZIDER WIRKUNG
PYRIDOTHIAZINES A ACTION HERBICIDE

(84) Designated Contracting States:
AL AT BE BG CH CY CZ DE DK EE ES FI FR GB GR HR HU IE IS IT LI LT LU LV MC MK MT NL NO PL PT RO RS SE SI SK SM TR

(30) Priority: 23.03.2010 EP 10157419
23.03.2010 US 316461 P

(43) Date of publication of application: 29.01.2013 Bulletin 2013/05

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C07D 513/04 (2006.01) A21N 43/00 (2006.01)

(86) International application number:
PCT/EP2011/054129

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WO 2011/117152 (29.09.2011 Gazette 2011/38)

(85) References cited:
WO-A1-2009/063180 WO-A2-2010/023311

EP 2 550 280 B1

Note: Within nine months of the publication of the mention of the grant of the European patent in the European Patent Bulletin, any person may give notice to the European Patent Office of opposition to that patent, in accordance with the implementing Regulations. Notice of opposition shall not be deemed to have been filed until the opposition fee has been paid. (Art. 99(1) European Patent Convention).

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EP 2 550 280 B1
(continued)

No.	Formula	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵
5	A-76	1,1A	Cl		OCHF ₂	H
10	A-79	1,1A	Cl		SCH ₃	H
15	A-80	1,1A	Cl		H	H
20	A-81	1,1A	Cl		CH ₃	H
25	A-82	1,1A	Cl		CF ₃	H
30	A-83	1,1A	Cl		CHF ₂	H
35	A-84	1,1A	Cl		OCH ₃	H
40	A-85	1,1A	Cl		OCHF ₂	H
45	A-86	1,1A	Cl		SCH ₃	H
50	A-87	1,1A	Cl		H	H
55	A-88	1,1A	Cl		CH ₃	H
60	A-89	1,1A	Cl		CF ₃	H
65	A-90	1,1A	Cl		CHF ₂	H
70	A-91	1,1A	Cl		OCH ₃	H
75	A-92	1,1A	Cl		OCHF ₂	H
80	A-93	1,1A	Cl		SCH ₃	H

21

	Structure	Molecule Name	compound	smiles	location	patent	moleweight
1		Compound 2503	Table 10_Table A_A-78	CN(c(CO)= description		EP2550280B1	487.0
2		Compound 2492	Table 10_Table A_A-79	CN(c(CO)= description		EP2550280B1	467.0
3		Compound 2528	Table 10_Table A_A-80	CC(C1)ON=C description		EP2550280B1	435.0
4		Compound 2529	Table 10_Table A_A-81	CC(C1)ON=C description		EP2550280B1	449.0
5		Compound 2524	Table 10_Table A_A-82	CC(C1)ON=C description		EP2550280B1	503.0
6		Compound 2525	Table 10_Table A_A-83	CC(C1)ON=C description		EP2550280B1	485.0
7		Compound 2526	Table 10_Table A_A-84	CC(C1)ON=C description		EP2550280B1	465.0

Summary

Have collected
databases for many
areas of
cheminformatics

LLMs provide a path
for efficient Natural
Language access

Examples provided
for chemistry,
pharmaceutical and
patent applications

Acknowledgements of Workflow Partners

Raw
Data

Data
Curation

MolGenie
Lutz & Aleksei

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Integration

Data AI
LLM & Bot

Molecular Assets
Steve & Mike

Data
Visualization

DataWarrior
Google
Kineviz

Discovery
Team

Tudor & Alex

Questions and Discussion

Collaboration: The Magic
Happens Here

